

Synthesis of α -(2-Methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)alkylamines

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α -(2-Alkyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)ethylamines, prepared by Kachru and Pathak¹, were tested *in vitro* for amoebacidal activity by Kaushiva² who observed the activity to increase with alkylation, attaining the maximum value with alkyl as hexyl group. It would be worthwhile to determine the amoebacidal activity of some structural analogues in order to locate the seat of activity in the amines described by Kachru and Pathak¹. The synthesis of α -(2-methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)alkylamines (II: R=Et, *n*-Pr, *n*-amyl) is recorded here.

Homoveratrole, prepared according to the procedure of Luff *et al.*³, was subjected to the Friedel-Crafts acylation with propionyl chloride, *n*-butyryl chloride, and caproyl chloride in CS₂ solution in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to furnish 2-methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl alkyl ketones (I: R = Et, *n*-Pr, *n*-amyl). Profuse demethylation occurred during the acylation. The demethylated ketones were, however, methylated and thus the ketones (I) were obtained in excellent yields. The ketoximes separated as viscous oils. The crude oils as such were reduced with metallic sodium and ethanol to provide the corresponding α -(2-methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)alkylamines (II).

TABLE I

2-Methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl alkyl ketone (I).

No.	R.	B.P.	Ketones.		Semicarbazones.		%Nitrogen	
			**M.P.	Yield.	**M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Et*	165°/5mm	40°	82%	140°	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂	15.6	15.8
2	<i>n</i> -Pr	180°/7	48°	81	200°	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂	14.8	15.1
3	<i>n</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁ †	190°/8	48°	73	128°	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂	13.4	13.7

*Phenyldiazone crystallised from dilute ethanol. m.p. 165°.

† " " " " acetic acid, m.p. 133°.

**Crystallised from dilute ethanol.

1. *This Journal*, 1957, 24, 768.

2. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, 16C, 234.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1134.

The various constants of the ketones (I) and amines (II) are recorded in Tables I and II, respectively.

TABLE II
 α -(2-Methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)alkylamines (II).

	R.	B.P.	% Yield.	Hydrochlorides.		% Nitrogen.		Picrate. M.P.
				*M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	
1	Et	148-54°/8mm	60 %	205°	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCl	5.6	5.7	†192°
2	n-Pr	160-65°/8	60	198°	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ NCl	6.2	5.4	†180°(d)
3	n-C ₃ H ₇	178.30°/8	63	190°	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ NCl	4.5	4.8	‡174°

*Crystallised from EtAc and EtOH.

† " " dil. ethanol

‡ " " water.

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